

Pheromone synthesis. Part-209[†] : Synthesis of candidate structures for homosesquiterpene alcohols found as a putative sex pheromone from the sandfly *Lutzomyia lichyi*

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Racemic and diastereomeric mixture of three homosesquiterpene alcohols 2, 3 and 4 were synthesized from a racemic and diastereomeric mixture of 3-methyl- α -himachalene (1) or from its synthetic precursor, 2-nor-ketone (5). These alcohols 2, 3 and 4 exhibited mass spectra not identical with those reported for the homosesquiterpene alcohols found as a putative sex pheromone in the hexane extract of the male sandfly *Lutzomyia lichyi*.

The sandfly *Lutzomyia lichyi* is a suggested secondary vector of *Leishmania* in Colombia, South America. This insect is taxonomically very closely related to *L. longipalpis* from Lapinha, Brazil, whose male-produced sex pheromone is shown to be (1*S*,3*S*,7*R*)-3-methyl- α -himachalene (1)¹. In 1999, Hamilton *et al.*² analyzed by GC-MS the hexane extracts of male *L. lichyi*, and revealed the presence of two new oxygenated homosesquiterpenes, which seemed to be a primary and tertiary alcohol. Hamilton *et al.* regarded them as a putative sex pheromone and hypothesized that they are related to 3-methyl- α -himachalene, because their MS are similar to that of 1².

Our continuing interest in the sandfly pheromone^{1,3,4} urged us to attempt the synthesis of some candidate structures for the homosesquiterpene alcohols such as 2, 3 and 4, which are the hydration products of 1. Because we had a small amount of the racemic and diastereomeric mixture of 1⁵, it seemed easy to prepare 2, 3 and 4 from 1 or its synthetic precursor, 2-nor-ketone 5⁵ as racemic and diastereomeric mixtures, which might be useful for MS comparison.

As shown in Fig. 1, primary alcohol 2 was prepared by hydroboration-oxidation of 1 in 51% yield. Addition of methyl lithium to 2-nor-ketone 5 furnished 3, one of the tertiary alcohols, in 86% yield. Regioselective epoxidation of 1 with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (MCPBA) afforded epoxide 6 (66%), which was reduced with lithium in liquid ammonia to give another tertiary alcohol 4 in 70% yield. For the reduction of 6 to 4, other reducing agents such as lithium aluminum hydride did not give good results.

Fig. 2 shows the EI-MS spectra of 2, 3 and 4, measured

Fig. 1. Synthesis of the alcohols 2, 3 and 4

[†]Part-208 T. Tashiro, M. Bando and K. Mori, *Synthesis*, 2000, 1852

on a Shimadzu GC-MS (QP5050A) analyzer. Although our synthetic products were racemic and diastereomeric mixtures, the stereoisomers of **2**, **3** or **4** as analyzed by GC-MS showed the mass fragmentation patterns not so different from each other. Comparison of our MS with the published spectra of the primary and tertiary alcohols² suggested their non-identity. In the spectrum of **2**, an intense peak at m/z 177, which was observed in the spectrum of the naturally occurring primary alcohol, was missing. The fragmentation pattern of **3** was quite different from that of the natural tertiary alcohol, while that of **4** was, to a certain extent, slightly similar to that of the natural alcohol. For further investigation, especially as to **4**, our samples of **2**, **3** and **4** were sent to Dr. Hamilton for direct comparison.

Fig. 2. Electron impact mass spectra of (a) primary alcohol **2**, (b) tertiary alcohol **3**, and (c) tertiary alcohol **4**

In conclusion, the two homosesquiterpene alcohols produced by male *L. lychyi* are suggested to possess structures different from **2**, **3** and **4**. We must await for the isolation of *L. lychyi* alcohols in amounts sufficient for their NMR analyses to propose the plausible structures.

Experimental

IR spectra were measured on a Jasco A-102 spectrometer, ¹H NMR spectra were recorded at 90 MHz on a Jeol EX-90A or at 400 MHz on a Jeol JNM-LA400 spectrometer. The peak for TMS (δ 0.00) or solvent (CHCl₃, δ 7.26) was used as the internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol JMS-SX102A or a Hitachi M-80B mass spectrometer. Refractive indices were measured on an ATAGO Abbe refractometer 1T. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis was carried out on a Shimadzu GC-MS QP5050A.

2-Hydroxymethyl-3,6,6,9-tetramethylbicyclo[5.4.0]undec-8-ene (2): To a solution of 3-methyl- α -himachalene **1** (racemic and diastereomeric mixture, 137 mg, 0.63 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added a solution of 9-BBN in THF (0.5 M solution; 1.9 ml, 0.95 mmol) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature, then 6 M aq. NaOH solution (1 ml) and 34.5% aqueous H₂O₂ (2 ml) were slowly added successively, and stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The mixture was diluted with Et₂O (10 ml), and the aqueous phase was extracted with Et₂O (2 × 10 ml). The combined organic layers was washed with sat. aq. NaHCO₃ solution and brine, dried with MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by chromatography on silica gel (8 g, elution with hexane/ethyl acetate, 50 : 3) to give **2** (75 mg, 51%) as a colorless oil. It was found to be contaminated with 24% of inseparable impurities [checked by GC analysis (column : DB-5[®])], $n_D^{24} = 1.5026$; ν_{\max} (film) 3350s (OH), 1450s, 1360m, 1040s, 1010m, 990m cm⁻¹; δ_H (400 MHz; CDCl₃) 0.84–1.01 (9H, m, 3-CH₃, 2 × 6-CH₃), 1.20–1.72 (12H, m, 1,2,3-H, 4,5,10,11-H₂, OH), 1.84–1.91 (3H, m, 9-CH₃), 1.94–2.14 (1H, m, 7-H), 3.54–3.87 (2H, m, CH₂OH), 5.24–5.57 (1H, m, 8-H); HRMS 236.2143. C₁₆H₂₈O requires m/z 236.2140; GC-MS [column : DB-5[®], carrier : He, 100 kPa, temp. 40° (2 min) then 40 + 10°/min to 250°, t_R = 19.4–20.5 min (each one of the eight peaks showed similar MS, although the relative intensities of the fragment ions were not completely identical)]. Due to its volatility no correct combustion analytical data of **2** could be obtained.

2-Hydroxy-2,3,6,6,9-pentamethylbicyclo[5.4.0]undec-8-ene (3): To a solution of the known ketone **5** (racemic and diastereomeric mixture, 110 mg, 0.50 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added a solution of MeLi in Et₂O (1.14 M; 2.5 ml, 2.9 mmol) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0°, and then it was poured into sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution. The aqueous phase was extracted with Et₂O (2 × 20 ml) and the combined organic layers washed with sat. aq. NaHCO₃ solution and brine, dried with MgSO₄, and con-

centrated *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by chromatography on silica gel (6 g, elution with hexane/ethyl acetate, 50 : 1) to give **3** (102 mg, 86%) as a colorless oil, $\eta_D^{25} = 1.5060$; ν_{\max} (film) 3500s (OH), 1690m, 1460s, 1450s, 1390m, 1365s, 1160m, 910s, 850m, 760m cm^{-1} ; δ_H (400 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.60–0.98 (9H, m, 3- CH_3 , 2 \times 6- CH_3), 0.99–1.89 (10H, m, 3-H, 4,5,10,11- H_2 , OH), 1.07–1.24 (3H, m, 2- CH_3), 1.67 (3H, br s, 9- CH_3), 1.94–2.46 (2H, m, 1,7-H), 5.46–5.68 (1H, m, 8-H); HRMS 236.2136. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}$ requires m/z 236.2140; GC-MS [column : DB-5[®], carrier : He, 100 kPa, temp. 40° (2 min), then 40 + 10°/min to 250°, $t_R = 15.6$ –18.5 min (each one of the seven peaks showed similar MS, although the relative intensities of the fragment ions were not identical)]. Due to its volatility no correct combustion analytical data of **3** could be obtained.

8,9-Epoxy-2-methylene-3,6,6,9-tetramethylbicyclo[5.4.0]undecane (4) : To a solution of **1** (racemic and diastereomeric mixture, 121 mg, 0.555 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) were added a mixture of MCPBA (70% purity; 156 mg, 86.0 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) and NaHCO_3 (115 mg, 1.37 mmol) at -10° . The reaction mixture was allowed to warm up to room temperature and stirred for 40 min. It was then poured into a sat. aq. Na_2SO_3 solution (10 ml). The mixture was stirred vigorously at room temperature for 30 min. The aqueous phase was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (2 \times 5 ml) and the combined organic layers washed with sat. aq. NaHCO_3 solution and brine, dried with MgSO_4 , and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by chromatography on silica gel (8 g, pentane/ethyl acetate, 50 : 2) to give **4** (86.4 mg, 66%) as a colorless oil. This was used in the next step without further purification, $\eta_D^{24} = 1.4912$; ν_{\max} (film) 1635m (C=C), 1450s, 1390m, 1380m, 1370m, 1125m, 890s, 825m, 800s, 670m cm^{-1} ; δ_H (400 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.86–1.22 (9H, m, 3- CH_3 , 2 \times 6- CH_3), 1.23–1.61 (8H, m, 4,5,10,11- H_2), 1.33 (3H, s, 9- CH_3), 1.62–2.06 (3H, m, 1,3,7-H), 2.47–3.09 (1H, m, 8-H), 4.71–4.88 (2H, m, = CH_2).

9-Hydroxy-2-methylene-3,6,6,9-tetramethylbicyclo[5.4.0]undecane (4) : To liq. NH_3 (10 ml) was added lithium

metal (15 mg, 2.1 mmol) at -78° . After stirring at -78° for 1 h, a solution of **6** (9.4 mg, 0.040 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added slowly to the reaction mixture. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h and then poured into a sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (10 ml). It was stirred at room temperature for 12 h and then diluted with Et_2O (10 ml). The aqueous phase was extracted with Et_2O (2 \times 10 ml) and the combined organic layers washed with sat. aq. NaHCO_3 solution and brine, dried with MgSO_4 and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by chromatography on silica gel (20 g, elution with hexane/ethyl acetate, 20 : 1) to give **5** (6.5 mg, 70%) as a colorless oil, $\eta_D^{24} = 1.5039$; ν_{\max} (film) 3375s (OH), 1630m (C=C), 1620m (C=C), 1425s, 1360s, 1205m, 1120m, 970m, 880m cm^{-1} ; δ_H (400 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.76 (3H, s, 6- CH_3), 0.86 (3H, s, 6- CH_3), 1.04 (3H, d, J 7.2 Hz, 3- CH_3), 1.09–1.83 (12H, m, 7-H, 4,5,8,10,11- H_2 , OH), 1.23 (3H, s, 9- CH_3), 1.99 (1H, dt, J 2.9, 11 Hz, 1-H), 2.42 (1H, sext.-like, J 6 Hz, 3-H), 4.70 (1H, s, = CHaHb), 4.74 (1H, s, = CHaHb); HRMS 236.2134. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}$ requires m/z 236.2140; GC-MS [column : DB-5[®], carrier : He, 100 kPa, temp. 40° (2 min) then 40 + 10°/min to 250°, $t_R = 17.7$ –18.8 min (each one of the four peaks showed similar MS, although the relative intensities of the fragment ions were not identical)]. Due to its volatility no correct combustion analytical data of **4** could be obtained.

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